

Effect of blue green algae (BGA) on rice yield at different locations and residual effect on gram

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We studied the effect of BGA on rice yields in multilocal trials by the JNKVV ARS in Bilaspur, MP, from 1979 to 1983 (Table 1). Applying 10 kg BGA inoculum/ha increased grain yield (14%).

Table 1. Grain yield with and without BGA, JNKVV.

Location	Grain yield (t/ha)		Increase in grain yield	
	Control (no BGA)	With 10 kg BGA/ha	t/ha	%
1979				
Sarkanda	3.4	4.1	0.7	19
Khoksa	3.2	3.5	0.3	10
Gorela	2.6	3.0	0.3	13
Ragja	1.1	1.1	0.1	7
1980				
Barkanda	3.4	4.0	0.6	18
Khoksa	3.0	3.4	0.4	13
Pendra	2.6	3.0	0.4	15
Dharampura	1.5	2.0	0.5	33
1981				
Sarkanda	2.4	2.8	0.4	17
Khoksa	1.7	2.0	0.3	19
Ragja	3.0	3.4	0.3	11
Lormi	2.6	3.0	0.4	15
Korba	2.7	3.0	0.3	13
Katghora	1.4	1.6	0.2	16
Gorela	2.8	3.1	0.3	10
1982				
Sarkanda	4.0	4.6	0.7	17
Jali	1.3	1.4	0.2	12
Kudri	2.2	2.3	0.2	7
Janjgir	2.4	2.5	0.2	6
Khisora	3.4	3.8	0.4	12
Khatola	2.4	2.8	0.4	17
Sakti	2.6	2.8	0.2	8
Churi	3.5	4.0	0.5	14
Pali	3.4	3.8	0.3	9
1983				
Bilaspur	2.3	2.8	0.5	20
Bilaspur	2.9	3.4	0.6	20
Mungeli	1.8	2.0	0.2	9
Mungeli	1.6	1.8	0.2	14
Lormi	3.4	3.6	0.2	5
Lormi	2.9	3.0	0.2	6
Pamgarh	2.8	3.2	0.4	14
Pamgarh	1.7	2.1	0.4	22
Katghora	3.5	4.5	1.0	29
Katghora	5.5	6.3	0.9	16
Av	2.7	3.1	0.4	14

Table 2. Grain yield with NPK and BGA at 4 locations, JNKVV.

Treatment (kg/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)							
	1979				1981			
	Sarkanda	Khoksa	Ragja	Pendra	Ragja	Khoksa	Sarkanda	Sarkanda
Control	3.4	3.2	1.0	2.6	3.0	1.7	23.58	4.0
10 BGA,	4.1	3.5	1.1	3.0	3.4	2.0	27.58	4.6
20-40-15 NPK	-	-	-	-	3.3	2.7	30.47	5.3
20-40-15 NPK + 10 BGA	-	-	-	-	3.7	2.8	30.43	6.0
40-40-15 NPK	4.3	3.2	1.2	3.3	3.8	2.6	32.57	5.5
40-40-15 NPK + 10 BGA	4.4	3.4	1.5	3.8	3.8	2.8	35.77	6.2
60-60-15 NPK	5.3	4.1	1.6	4.0	4.0	2.6	39.06	6.2
60-60-15 NPK + 10 BGA	-	-	-	-	4.0	2.9	39.29	6.5
CD at 5%	-	0.6	-	-	0.4	0.6	0.4	1.2

Trials in 1979, 1981, and 1982 (Table 2) show that applying 10 kg BGA/ha saves 20-40 kg N/ha.

In 1979, we evaluated the yield of Bengal gram planted after rice to determine the residual effect of 10 kg BGA inoculation/ha to rice (Table 3); BGA was inoculated before rice transplanting. Gram was drilled immediately after rice harvest without plowing the field. No fertilizer was applied and the crop was grown without management. Table 3

Table 3. Yield of rice and gram after rice, JNKVV.

Treatment (kg/ha)	Rice yield (t/ha)	Gram yield (t/ha)
Control	3.4	1.2
10 BGA	4.1	1.8
40-40-15 NPK	4.3	1.8
40-40-15 NPK + 10 BGA	4.4	1.4

shows that BGA increased rice and gram yield. □

Yield response of upland rice to NPK fertilization with burned rice husk

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We conducted a field experiment to determine the effect of applying N, P, and K with and without burned rice husk. Soil was a Gleyic Luvisol with 32.1% sand, 36.8% silt, 31.1% clay, pH 5.3, 1.36% organic carbon, 0.18% total N, 37 ppm available P, 0.5 meq exchangeable K/100

g, and 16.74 meq cation exchange capacity/100 g.

Before direct-seeding 120 kg IR42 seeds/ha, 10 t burned rice husk/ha was evenly applied and incorporated. Seeds

Table 2. Effect of NPK fertilizer and burned rice husk on grain yield of upland rice, Sabah, Malaysia.

Fertilizer applied (kg/ha) NPK	Grain yield ^a (t/ha)			
	Without rice husk		With rice husk	
0-0-0	0.9	i	1.5	i
50-0-0	1.3	gh	2.3	def ^g
100-0-0	1.6	ef	2.7	def ^g
150-0-0	1.9	e	2.9	cd
0-13-0	1.0	i	1.8	h
50-13-0	2.4	cd	3.0	c
100-13-0	2.6	c	3.9	a
150-13-0	2.9	b	3.8	a
0-13-25	1.4	fg	2.8	def
50-13-25	2.6	c	3.0	c
100-13-25	3.1	b	3.1	c
150-13-25	3.5	a	3.3	b

^aIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 0.05 level by DMRT.

Table 1. Weekly rainfall distribution during crop season, Sabah, Malaysia.

Mo	Rainfall (mm)				
	Wk1	Wk2	Wk3	Wk4	Total
Jul	85.0	12.0	18.1	12.2	127.3
Aug	24.1	32.0	0	43.1	99.2
Sep	0	0	68.5	36.0	104.5
Oct	58.4	81.1	15.6	4.8	159.9
Nov	11.0	4.2	19.0	41.6	75.8

were sown in rows at 20-cm spacing. Zero, 50, 100, or 150 kg N/ha; 0 or 13 kg P/ha; and 0 or 25 kg K/ha were applied. P and K were applied at planting. N was applied in equal splits 1 mo after sowing and at panicle initiation. The experiment was in a split-plot design with three

replications.

Weekly rainfall at Timbang Menggaris is shown in Table 1. Rainfall distribution was uneven and interrupted by drought. Yields were low because of low agronomic efficiency of applied fertilizer.

Significantly higher grain yields were

obtained with 100-13-0 kg NPK with burned rice husk and 150-13-25 kg NPK without burned rice husk (Table 2). With burned rice husk, high N and K did not increase the grain yield, but results suggest that 10 t burned rice husk/ha supplies 55-3-70 kg NPK/ha to rice. □

Effect of different nitrogen applications on rice grain yield

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We studied the effect of different N applications on IR6 yield at the Gomal

University Research Farm. Soil was a Zindani series of Entisols with 17% clay, 65% silt, 18% sand, 15.6% CaCO₃, 0.6% organic matter, pH 7.9, 4 ppm available P, 160 ppm K, and 3.5 ppm Zn. Twenty-seven kg P/ha as a single superphosphate (9% P) was applied basally, and different levels of N were incorporated in dry soil. Soil was flooded and the field was transplanted.

Results were highly significant. IR6 yielded highest (8.1 t/ha) with 138 kg N/ha as urea (see table). All fertilizer treatments increased yield significantly over the no-fertilizer treatment. Split-N-application plots yielded less than full application in dry soil, which produced highest straw yield, plant height, panicles/m², 1,000 grain weight, and net return/ha. □

Effect of different N applications on rice yield, Pakistan, 1982.

N (kg/ha)	Application method	Yield ^a (t/ha)		Increase (t/ha) over no-fertilizer		Net return ^b (US\$/ha)	Plant ht (cm)	Panicles (no./m ²)	1,000-grain wt (g)
		Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw				
Control	—	5.3 d	10.6 c	—	—	—	86.7	422	25.3
46	Basal application on dry soil before flooding	6.1 cd	11.8 bc	0.8	1.2	54.3	87.1	436	27.3
92	Basal application on dry soil before flooding	7.3 ab	14.3 ab	2.0	3.7	137.7	91.3	467	28.3
138	Basal application on dry soil before flooding	8.1 a	15.2 a	2.8	4.6	192.0	98.1	510	30.0
46	Equal splits on dry soil before flooding and 7-8 wk after transplanting	7.1 bc	13.6 ab	1.8	3.0	140.0	90.0	483	27.3
92	Equal splits on dry soil before flooding and 7-8 wk after transplanting	6.8 bc	14.7 a	1.5	4.1	94.8	92.1	486	27.7
138	Equal splits on dry soil before flooding and 7-8 wk after transplanting	6.8 bc	12.8 abc	1.5	2.2	78.0	87.4	486	28.0
92	Conventional (30+31+31)	7.0 bc	15.0 a	1.7	4.4	109.4	91.3	458	27.3

^a Means followed by similar letters are not significantly different at the 5% level. ^b Rice = \$86/t; urea fertilizer = US\$8.5/23 kg N.

Effect of bio, organic, and chemical fertilizers on rice grain yield

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We studied the effect of combined application of bio, organic, and chemical fertilizers on IR20 grain yield at TNRRI in Aug-Jan 1983. Soil was an alluvial clay loam with 137 ppm available N (alkaline permanganate method), 35 meq CEC/100 g, and pH 6.6.

The experiment was in a randomized block design with three replications. Forty kg PK/ha was applied with 60 or 90 kg N as urea, farmyard manure (FYM) 0.609% N, green manure (Gm) 0.518% N fresh weight, and azolla 0.395% fresh weight. Fertilizers were incorporated 1 wk before transplanting.

N application increased grain yield significantly over the control (see table). At 60 kg N, urea alone performed better than in combination with organic manures. At 90 kg N, urea + azolla performed better than urea alone. At both N levels combinations with azolla performed best.

Effect of bio, organic, and inorganic fertilizers on grain yield, Aduthurai, India.

Treatment (kg N/ha)	Grain yield (t/ha)
Control	3.5
30 as urea + 30 as FYM	3.8
30 as urea + 30 as Gm	4.1
30 as urea + 30 as azolla	4.2
60 as urea	4.3
45 as urea + 45 as FYM	4.3
45 as urea + 45 as Gm	4.6
45 as urea + 45 as azolla	5.1
90 as urea	4.9
CD	0.4